

THE TALENT ACQUISITION PROCESS CONDUCTED IN ATM RECRUITMENT CONSULTANCY

Dr. J. Ravi

Associate Professor, School of Management Studies,
REVA University, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India.
Email: jravistat@gmail.com

Dr. Madhavi Kappagantula

Associate Professor, School of Management Studies,
REVA University, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India.
Email: madhavi.kappagantula@reva.edu.in

Dr. B. Udaya Bhaskara Ganesh

Assistant Professor, Department of Management Studies,
Gayatri vidya Parishad College of Engineering (Autonomous) Visakhapatnam, India.
Email: ganesh.uday6@gmail.com

Abstract

The article focuses on the research of the talent acquisition process. ATM Recruitment Consultancy did a research on the talent acquisition Process, which revealed a variety of facts regarding the company's talent acquisition technique. Using this study, the researcher was able to determine the recruitment modules used in the business, various criteria considered for the talent acquisition process, and employee satisfaction with Recruiting. How they determine the good requirements and achieve the goal of selecting the applicant

Keywords: *ATM, Recruitment, Consultancy, talent, employees.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Recruitment is the practice of seeking out potential workers and encouraging them to apply for positions inside the firm. Selection may be described as the process by which an organization selects from among applicants those individuals who they believe would best fit the job requirements in light of the existing environmental conditions. The primary goal of this research for ATM Recruitment Consultancy's talent acquisition procedure. Secondary goals include determining whether recruitment is done internally or externally, analyzing the effectiveness of the talent acquisition process, identifying the factors of the talent acquisition process, identifying new ways to improve the current recruitment procedure, and determining the average time spent on the selection process. A questionnaire was utilized to obtain data from the sample in this investigation. The stratified sampling strategy is utilized in this investigation. The research has a sample size of 145 people. Two-way ANOVA, Chi-Square, and Rank Correlation are the methods employed in this investigation. This research assists organizations in making decisions in selecting the right individuals for the right position, identifying areas of concern, and suggesting strategies to enhance the talent acquisition process. This research focuses on understanding the talent acquisition process; it assists in managing a personnel budget for the talent acquisition process; and it assists in evaluating the time constraints for the recruiting process.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Finding possible candidates for current and future organisational openings is known as recruiting. In other words, it is a "connecting activity" that brings people who have jobs and people who are looking for jobs together.

The steps most frequently followed when creating an HR strategy are:

Establishing the strategic course, the creation of the human resource management system, creating the necessary human resources, planning the entire staff, investing in the performance and development of human resources evaluating and maintaining organisational performance and competence.

Basic Human Resource Management Overviews, Finding the best employees, paying them (and giving them benefits), training them, making sure they follow rules, creating safe working conditions, and keeping them.

The technical requirements include technical expertise, professional abilities, and industry experience. The most important factors in the French hiring process are the candidate's charisma and personality. To guarantee a smooth flow of information between the company and its subsidiary, communication skills and language proficiency are also crucial.

3. OBJECT OF THE STUDY

3.1 Primary Objectives

- To assess the employee perception towards the talent acquisition process in ATM Recruitment Consultancy.

3.2 Secondary Objectives

- To evaluate the employers' perceptions of the hiring process they went through.
- To specify whether employees are hired internally or externally.
- To evaluate the efficiency of the hiring process.
- To recognize the components of the talent acquisition process.
- To find innovative solutions to enhance the current hiring process.
- To determine the typical duration of the selecting process.

3.3 Need for the Study

Human resource management is a new scientific subject in this age of fast technological growth. Human resources will have a significant impact on an organization's performance in today's internationally competitive and demanding business environment. People in charge of making things happen are managed. In today's world, it is critical to efficiently acquire people since they are the organization's most valuable asset.

Determine the organization's current and future staff needs via job planning and analysis. Understanding the organization's talent acquisition process. Budgetary Analysis of Human Resources Time management in the recruitment process is examined.

3.4 Scope of the Study

In today's quickly evolving corporate world, organizations must quickly adapt to human requirements. In order to discover the best applicants for available positions, it is crucial to have a well-defined recruiting policy in place that can be effectively applied. If the wrong candidate is selected or the right one is turned down, the organization might suffer severe losses. One area where outside factors have minimal impact is selection. In order to get the best results, the HR department can use its discretion while creating its selection strategy and implementing several selection techniques. As a result, complete commitment and involvement should be shown while hiring staff in order to determine the recruitment strategy used by responders. The scope of the investigation is described as follows:

- This research assists in choosing the best individuals for the appropriate positions.
- This research aids the business in pinpointing the area of concern and making recommendations for methods to enhance the recruiting and selection process.
- This research focuses on the process of finding new talent.
- This research assists in managing a personnel budget for the hiring of talent.
- This study aids in determining how much time is available for the recruiting procedure.

3.5 Limitations of the Study

- Feedback only expresses the opinions of a small number of responders and is not always indicative of the total population.
- Time was a huge restriction, and people weren't particularly receptive.
- The absence of secondary data.
- The research employed a smaller sample size.
- An employee is afraid to bring up the bad points.
- The information gathered is based on the respondents' perceptions.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A research methodology is a systematic approach to tackling a research topic. It is an examination of the methods used in scientific investigation. The many steps a researcher typically follows to examine a research subject are examined, as well as the justification for each step. The researcher should be knowledgeable about research methods and techniques, including how to design particular tests, compute the mean, median, mode, or chi-square, apply a particular research strategy, identify which methods are effective and which are not, and understand what they signify and imply as well as why. It is important for researchers to understand the underlying assumptions of the various techniques. Research techniques are a subset of research methodology since it contains many different features.

4.1 Chi-Square Test:

The Chi-square Test is a useful tool for contrasting experimentally obtained results with those that were theoretically and hypothesis-based projected. The frequencies that should be uniformly spaced out over a particular amount of time are the predicted frequencies.

$$X^2 = \sum [(O-E)^2 / E]$$

Where, O-Observed frequency & E-Expected frequency.

4.2 Research Design

The decision of what, where, when, how much, and how to undertake a study or inquiry is known as the research design. It is defined as the setting up of conditions for data collection and analysis in a way that combines the economic approach with relevance to the research purpose. The many different research procedures must work together seamlessly for research to be as efficient as possible in terms of producing the most information with the least amount of work, time, and money. This is why research design is necessary. Since it acts as the firm foundation for the entire superstructure of the research effort, research design really has a considerable influence on how reliable the final results.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

5.1. Chi- Square Test (ψ^2)

The Chi-square is calculated by adding the squared differences between the observed (o) and expected (e) data (or the deviation, d), and dividing the result by the expected data over all conceivable categories.

Null hypothesis (Ho):

There is no relationship between the Education Qualification and Nature of Job.

Alternate hypothesis (H1):

There is a relationship between the Education Qualification and Nature of Job.

Table: Education Qualification & Nature of Job

Particulars			Nature of job			Total
			Trainee	Staff	Executive	
Education qualification	Diploma	Count	12	0	0	12
		% within education qualification	100.0%	.0%	.0%	100.0%
		% within nature of job	25.5%	.0%	.0%	10.0%
		% of total	10.0%	.0%	.0%	10.0%
	Ug	Count	35	8	0	43
		% within education qualification	81.4%	18.6%	.0%	100.0%
		% within nature of job	74.5%	15.1%	.0%	35.8%
		% of total	29.2%	6.7%	.0%	35.8%
	Pg	Count	0	45	20	65
		% within education qualification	.0%	69.2%	30.8%	100.0%
		% within nature of job	.0%	84.9%	100.0%	54.2%
		% of total	.0%	37.5%	16.7%	54.2%
	Total	Count	47	53	20	120
		% within education qualification	39.2%	44.2%	16.7%	100.0%
		% within nature of job	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% of total	39.2%	44.2%	16.7%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

Sources	Value	DF	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	94.205	4	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	124.845	4	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	70.320	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	120		

Degree of Freedom = (r-1) *(c-1) = 2*2= 4

Calculated value = 94.205 & Tabulated value = 9.488

Z = Z cal > Z tab. So, Z = 94.205 > 9.488. Hence, the Alternate hypothesis [H1] is accepted

Inference:

There is a link between the education requirement and the nature of the job because the calculated number is higher than the tabulated figure, which leads us to believe the alternate hypothesis.

5.2. Analysis Using Karl Pearson’s Correlation

The statistical technique of correlation analysis is used to ascertain how linearly related two variables are. Correlation measures how closely two variables are related to one another.

Null hypothesis (H0):

There is positive relationship between the Education qualification is considered while selecting a candidate and Technical skill is considered while selecting a candidate.

Alternate hypothesis (H1):

There is negative relationship between the Education qualification is considered while selecting a candidate and Technical skill is considered while selecting a candidate.

Correlations Analysis

Particulars		Education qualification is considered while selecting a candidate	Technical skill is considered while selecting a candidate
Education qualification is considered while selecting a candidate	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1	0.903**
	N	120	120
Technical skill is considered while selecting a candidate	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	0.903**	1
	N	120	120

$$r = \frac{N\sum XY - \sum X\sum Y}{\sqrt{N\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2} \sqrt{N\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2}}$$

r = .903

Inference:

Since r is positive, there is a positive correlation between the technical competence and education qualification that are taken into account when choosing a candidate.

6. FINDINGS & SUGGESTIONS

6.1 Findings

- 1) The majority of replies are women
- 2) The majority of responses are between the ages of 21 and 30.
- 3) Most survey participants are married.
- 4) The majority of responders earn more than RS.10000 each month.
- 5) Post-graduates make up the majority of replies
- 6) The majority of responders have had less than 1 year of experience
- 7) Staff makes up the majority of respondents.
- 8) Campus interviews account for the recruitment of the majority of respondents, whereas consulting accounts for 9% of respondents.
- 9) The majority of respondents concur that the company's referral policy is in place.
- 10) The business rewards its employees who refer customers at 100%.
- 11) The majority of respondents favour external hiring.
- 12) The majority of responders have gone through three stages. Every single responder is happy with the manner in which the interview was done.
- 13) The majority of respondents said the interview panel did a great job.
- 14) The majority of responders spent 11 to 20 minutes.
- 15) The majority of respondents like in-person interviews.
- 16) The majority of respondents believe that there are various procedures for various employee grades.
- 17) The majority of responders pick aptitude.
- 18) The majority of respondents believe that innovative approaches should be used extensively.
- 19) The majority of respondents indicated that ATM Recruitment Consultancy's talent acquisition process does not require any changes.
- 20) The majority of respondents firmly concur that choosing a candidate requires consideration of the individual's job experience.
- 21) The majority of responders firmly concur that technical expertise is necessary.
- 22) The majority of responders highly concur about English fluency.
- 23) The majority of responders strongly concur with the statement "Good intellectual."

- 24) The majority of respondents have placed 1 for educational credentials at the junior level. 35.9 percent of respondents rated it third,
- 25) Five percent of respondents ranked it second, and 38.6 percent of respondents ranked it first in the junior level of experience. Most of the respondents gave it a 1.
- 26) Rating for communicating at the junior level. Most of the respondents gave it a 1 for leadership abilities at the junior level.
- 27) Twenty-seven. At a Middle Level of Qualification Most respondents gave it a rating of 1. Most of the respondents gave it a score of 1 29 for the Middle level of Experience. Most of the respondents rated communication at the middle level at 1 out of 30. Most of the respondents gave it an average rating of 1 31 for leadership skills at the middle level. Before joining 32, the majority of respondents were familiar with the company's policies. The majority of respondents placed the Naukri in the top 33. The Times position had an average ranking of 34 from the respondents. The Monster is picked first out of 35 by the majority of responders. The majority of respondents placed the click in jobs as third.
- 28) The majority of those surveyed placed it fourth.
- 29) Every single responder agrees that the business is gathering feedback following the hiring procedure.
- 30) The majority of respondents firmly concur that direct applicants are the source of possible candidates. The following proportion of candidates accepted after being sourced by placement consultants the majority of respondents strongly agreed, while 24.8% of respondents indicated they were unsure.
- 31) The majority of respondents firmly concur that job sites serve as a source of possible candidates.
- 32) The majority of responders firmly concur that employees are the source of potential candidates.
- 33) The majority of respondents firmly concur that headhunting produces prospective candidates.
- 34) The majority of responders, 35, firmly concur that the potential candidate is produced by body shopping.
- 35) The majority of respondents—66.9% of them—believe that ATM Recruitment Consultancy's talent acquisition method is excellent or even very good.

6.2. Suggestions

1. The majority of respondents believe that the talent acquisition process needs to be modified. The business must make certain adjustments, such as employing fresh methods for hiring and taking more time when choosing staff.
2. For hiring purposes, the organization solely uses employment sites, consulting, casual applications, and campus interviews. It is advised that the organization use additional channels to find personnel, such as the employment exchange, periodicals, and newspapers. The company can increase their candidate pool through internal sources.
3. Before entering the firm, many of the candidates are unaware of the corporate policies. Candidates might receive training to help them understand the corporate policies fully.
4. The business may do more to enhance the recruitment and selection process. The majority of employees are unaware of video conferencing, thus in the future, the business should use it to interview applicants in order to save time.

5. Organizations may utilize the web extensively to streamline, expedite, reduce the cost, and improve the effectiveness of recruiting. The hiring process shouldn't be overly drawn out or time-consuming.
6. By tailoring the hiring procedure to each grade level, they may prevent wasting time on candidates while waiting for experienced candidates.
7. At every stage of the process, time management should be emphasized and should not be neglected. The company should broaden its selection criteria beyond campus placement and staff recommendations to include things like ads and e-recruitment.
8. E-Recruitment is used by 95.5 percent of businesses to pool prospects. The business might also concentrate on finding personnel through other channels. It is advised to take additional aspects like experience, leadership potential, and communication skills into account when hiring junior-level staff in addition to the certification requirement.
9. Other variables, such as qualifications, leadership abilities, and communication skills, should be taken into consideration when hiring middle-level staff in addition to the experience element.

7. CONCLUSION

Most workers were happy, but modifications are needed to reflect the changing circumstances, since the recruiting process has a significant influence on the firm's operations as new blood and ideas join the organization. The selection method is nice, but it should be changed according to the criteria and job profile so that the main goal of picking the applicant can be met. Further, I hope that the company will profit from this study, and that with the aid of the ideas provided, the organization may enhance its functioning and the overall Talent acquisition Process in the business, as well as its performance.

The conclusion is based on a study and study conducted by the organization regarding the Talent Acquisition Process. ATM Recruitment Consultancy did a research on the Talent Acquisition Process, which yielded a variety of facts concerning the company's talent acquisition method. Using this study, the researcher was able to determine the recruitment modules used in the business, various criteria considered for the talent acquisition process, and employee satisfaction with Recruiting.

Most workers were happy, but improvements are necessary to reflect the changing circumstances, since the recruiting process has a significant influence on the firm's operations as new blood and ideas join the organization. The selection method is nice, but it should be updated based on the needs and job profile so that the main goal of picking the applicant can be met. Further, I hope that the company will benefit from this study and that with the aid of the advice provided, the organization may enhance its functioning and the overall Talent acquisition Process in the organization, and its performance will improve.

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